

COMPARISON ON REFLECTION/TRANSMISSION COEFFICIENT

Final Report

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1. Introduction

A comparison on scattering coefficients with Type N connectors was planned among the partners of the EPM (European Partnership on Metrology) project. This inter-laboratory comparison exercise was part of the project “Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II” (22RPT04 ‘RFMicrowave2’), under Work Package (WP) 1.3 titled “Reflection and transmission coefficients (S-parameters) and attenuation measurement”.

The comparison was planned for three participants (TÜBİTAK UME, IMBIH and SIQ) involved in WP 1.3 of “22RPT04 RFMicrowave2” Project.

The comparison was conducted in accordance with the Technical Protocol prepared by TÜBİTAK UME and approved by the participants.

SPARK provided the attenuator for the comparison.

The comparison was carried out by measuring the S-parameters at eight frequencies which were 50 MHz, 500 MHz, 1 GHz, 2 GHz, 3 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz, and 18 GHz.

IMBIH and TÜBİTAK was responsible for analyzing and reporting the results of the comparison respectively.

2. Participants of the Comparison

2.1. Participants

List of participating laboratories is given in Table 1.

Table 1. List of participating laboratories

Country	Institute	Acronym	Shipping Address	Contact Person
Turkey	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü	TÜBİTAK UME	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, TURKEY	Handan SAKARYA Tel: +90 262 679 50 00 Fax: +90 262 679 50 01 handan.sakarya@tubitak.gov.tr
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Institut za Mjeriteljstvo Bosne i Hercegovine	IMBiH	Institut za mjeriteljstvo Bosne i Hercegovine (IMBiH) Branilaca Sarajeva 25, 71000 Sarajevo, BOSNA IN HERCEGOVINA	Osman SIBONJIC osman.sibonjic@met.gov.ba
Slovenia	Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje	SIQ	Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje (SIQ) Mašera-Spasičeva 10 SI-1000 Ljubljana SLOVENIA	Marko BERGINC Marco.berginc@siq.si Tel: +386 1 4778 340

2.2. Pilot Institute

This comparison was piloted by TÜBİTAK UME. The pilot institute is responsible for preparing the measurement instructions, controlling the stability of the travelling standard and preparing the comparison report. The evaluation of the comparison is performed by IMBiH.

3. Organisation of the Comparison

3.1. The time schedule

The time schedule for the comparison is given in the Table 2. The circulation of travelling standard was organized so that to monitor the performance of the travelling standard. Each laboratory had 2 weeks to carry out the measurements and 2 weeks for transportation.

Table 2. Circulation Time Schedule

Acronym of Institute	Country	Starting Date	Time for measurement and transportation
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	May 2025	2 weeks
IMBiH	Bosnia and Herzegovina	June 2025	2 weeks
SIQ	Slovenia	June 2025	2 weeks
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	August 2025	2 weeks

3.2. Unexpected events

No damages were reported on the travelling standards during the comparison.

4. Travelling Standard

The fixed attenuator used as travelling standard (Figure 1). Its identification is as follows:

Manufacturer : Agilent
 Model : 8491B
 Frequency Range : DC-18 GHz
 Serial Number : MY39269497

Figure 1. Representative photo of travelling standard

Within the comparison, the 50 MHz, 500 MHz, 1 GHz, 2 GHz, 3 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz and 18 GHz step frequencies measured. The participants submitted their measurement results for as many measuring points defined above as possible. The results expressed as attenuation in dB (S₂₁), real and imaginary for reflection (S₁₁) and its associated expanded uncertainty in two significant digits for a confidence level of 95 %.

The travelling standard is supplied by SPARK.

The travelling standard was packed in a transport case of size (25 x 15 x 30) cm and a total weight of 2 kg.

5. Measurement Instructions

The measurement instructions, describing the preliminary operations to be performed on the travelling standard were given in the Technical Protocol. The measurements were performed using Vector Network Analyser. Measurements were carried out at eight different frequencies for the cases of Reflection Coefficient in Complex (RCC) and attenuation in dB according to the (Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement) GUM.

6. Measurement Quantities and Points

The quantities to be measured and the measurement frequency points are given in Table 4.

Table 3. Measurement quantities & points

Quantity	Measured Attenuation (dB)	Measurement Frequency (GHz)
Transmission Coefficient	20	0.05
		0.5
		1
		2
		3
		10
		15
		18

7. Temperature and humidity during the comparison measurements

Acronym of Institute	Country	Temperature °C	Relative Humidity %rh
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	23 ± 1	45 ± 15
SIQ	Slovenia	23 ± 2	50 ± 20
IMBIH*	Bosnia and Herzegovina	23 ± 2	50 ± 20

*IMBIH is performed measurements at SIQ

8. Measurement Results of Participants

Each participant institute used Vector Network Analyser to measure the transmission and reflection coefficient of travelling standard.

The comparison was carried out at the following frequencies: .0.05 GHz, 0.5 GHz, 1 GHz, 2 GHz, 3 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz, and 18 GHz. However, since IMBIH's measurement capability is limited to 3 GHz, they were unable to perform measurements above 3 GHz. Therefore, calculations at points above 3 GHz were performed using only TÜBITAK UME and SIQ data.

The uncertainty of measurement was calculated according to GUM (Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), JCGM 100:2008) for the confidence level of 95 %.

9. The Comparison Reference Value (CRV)

The comparison reference value, CRV, is calculated separately for each frequency level. The CRV is considered as an estimation of the measurand according to the measurements provided by the participating laboratories. This estimation, y , is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties. The procedure is implemented in four steps:

1. **Comparison reference value $CRV(y)$** , using the inverse values of the squares of the uncertainties as the weights is determined using Eq. 1.

$$y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i \cdot u^{-2}(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)} \quad (1)$$

2. **Standard uncertainty of CRV, $u(y)$** , is calculated using (2).

$$u(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)}} \quad (2)$$

3. **Consistency of results:** A χ^2 test is applied to carry out an overall consistency check of the results obtained (*i.e.*, if all results can be regarded to belong to the same statistical ensemble). For each measurement, the observed chi-squared value χ_{obs}^2 is determined using Eq. 3. The number of degrees of freedom is $\nu=N-1$ for N results. The consistency check is considered failed if Eq. 4 is satisfied where Pr denotes *probability of*. If the χ^2 test fails, then the laboratory with the largest $|d_i|$ value (see below for definition) is excluded from the determination of the CRV and the consistency check is repeated. The process is then repeated as needed.

$$\chi_{obs}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - y)^2}{u^2(x_i)} \quad (3)$$

$$Pr\{\chi^2(\nu) > \chi_{obs}^2\} < 5\% \quad (4)$$

4. **Exclusion of incompatible results:** Compatibility index, d_i , is defined as the ratio between the difference from the reference value and the standard uncertainty, Eq. 5. The compatibility index $|d_i|$ describes the deviation from the CRV in relation to the calculated standard uncertainty of the deviation.

$$d_i = \frac{\Delta x_i}{u(\Delta x_i)} = \frac{x_i - y}{\sqrt{u^2(x_i) - u^2(y)}} \quad (5)$$

$$u^2(\Delta x_i) = u^2(x_i) + u^2(y) \quad (6)$$

5. **Degree of Equivalences (D_i) and Normalised Errors (E_n):** In each case, the degree of equivalence of laboratory i with the CRV will be determined as the pair of values for the deviation from the CRV and the uncertainty of this deviation [$\Delta x_i, u(\Delta x_i)$] according to Eq. 7, where $u(\Delta x_i)$ is obtained by applying Eq. 8.

$$E_n = \frac{\Delta x_i}{U(\Delta x_i)}$$

$$\Delta x_i = x_i - y \quad (7)$$

$$U(\Delta x_i) = 2 \cdot u(\Delta x_i)$$

$$u^2(\Delta x_i) = u^2(x_i) - u^2(y) \quad (8)$$

Note 1: The factor 2 in Eq. 7 indicates a coverage factor of 95% corresponding to a Gaussian distribution function.

Note 2: Eq. 8 establishes a difference of two variances as consequence of the mutual dependence (*i.e.*, correlation) between x_i and CRV .

The degree of equivalences and the normalised errors for each comparison points are presented in Appendix I in tables and in graphs respectively.

Table 4. The Comparison Reference Values of attenuator S21 logarithmic magnitude and phase according to the GUM

Frequency (GHz)	CRV(y) (dB)	$U(y)$ (dB)	CRV θ (°)	$U(\theta)$ (°)
0.05	19.931	0.011	-3.816	0.089
0.5	19.950	0.011	-37.670	0.073
1	19.969	0.011	-75.164	0.087
2	19.997	0.011	-150.146	0.087
3	20.018	0.011	134.887	0.095
10	19.987	0.015	-34.555	0.113
15	19.973	0.015	-63.998	0.118
18	20.177	0.015	56.551	0.119

Table 5. The Comparison Reference Values of attenuator S11 real and imaginary according to the GUM

Frequency (GHz)	CRVX(y)	$UX(y)$	CRVY(y)	$UY(y)$
0.05	-0.002	0.0006	0.0002	0.0006
0.5	-0.002	0.0007	0.0019	0.0007
1	-0.001	0.0008	0.0042	0.0008
2	0.005	0.0009	0.0100	0.0009
3	0.018	0.0009	0.0067	0.0011
10	0.012	0.0012	-0.0013	0.0014
15	0.015	0.0024	-0.0024	0.0018
18	-0.042	0.0026	0.0540	0.0024

Table 6. Consistency of results for the transmission and reflection coefficient S21 and S11

Frequency (GHz)	Transmission coefficient S21		Reflection coefficient S11	
	Magnitude	Phase	Real comp.	Imag.comp.
	χ^2_{abs}	$\chi^2_{abs}(\theta)$	$\chi^2_{abs}(X)$	$\chi^2_{abs}(Y)$
0.05	0.022	0.025	0.1217	0.0161
0.5	0.027	0.212	0.0351	0.0507
1	0.027	0.094	0.0089	0.0341
2	0.082	0.240	0.6548	0.0000
3	0.061	0.434	0.1875	0.1053
10	0.017	0.060	1.2544	0.2813
15	0.026	0.167	0.0064	0.5120
18	0.432	0.287	0.3354	1.2790

Table 7. Calculated chi - distribution for the magnitude (transmission coefficient S21)

Frequency (GHz)	Magnitude		
	χ^2_{abs}	N	chidist
0.05	0.022	3	0.99
0.5	0.027	3	0.99
1	0.027	3	0.99
2	0.082	3	0.96
3	0.061	3	0.97
10	0.017	2	0.90
15	0.026	2	0.87
18	0.432	2	0.51

Table 8. Calculated chi - distribution for the phase (transmission coefficient S21)

Frequency (GHz)	Phase		
	$\chi^2_{abs}(\theta)$	N	chidist
0.05	0.025	3	0.99
0.5	0.212	3	0.90
1	0.094	3	0.95
2	0.240	3	0.89
3	0.434	3	0.81
10	0.060	2	0.81
15	0.167	2	0.68
18	0.287	2	0.59

Table 9. Calculated chi - distribution for the real component (reflection coefficient S11)

Frequency (GHz)	Real comp.		
	$\chi^2_{abs}(X)$	N	chidist
0.05	0.1217	3	0.94
0.5	0.0351	3	0.98
1	0.0089	3	1.00
2	0.6548	3	0.72
3	0.1875	3	0.91
10	1.2544	2	0.26
15	0.0064	2	0.94
18	0.3354	2	0.56

Table 10. Calculated chi - distribution for the imaginary component (reflection coefficient S11)

Frequency (GHz)	Imag. comp		
	$\chi^2_{abs}(Y)$	N	chidist
0.05	0.0161	3	0.99
0.5	0.0507	3	0.97
1	0.0341	3	0.98
2	0.0000	3	1.00
3	0.1053	3	0.95
10	0.2813	2	0.60
15	0.5120	2	0.47
18	1.2790	2	0.26

10. Summary and Conclusions

A comparison of Transmission and Reflection Coefficient measurement using Vector Network Analyser was planned among the partners of the EMP (European Partnership on Metrology) project. This inter-laboratory comparison was part of the project “Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II” (22RPT04 ‘RFMicrowave2’).

Three participants from the “22RPT04 RFMicrowave2” project were involved in the comparison. The procedure followed a technical protocol prepared by TÜBİTAK UME, which was agreed upon by all participants.

The comparison was carried out by measuring s-parameters of a travelling standard, which was an Agilent 8491B model 20 dB attenuator. Measurements were done at eight different frequencies: 50 MHz, 500 MHz, 1 GHz, 2 GHz, 3 GHz, 10 GHz, 15 GHz and 18 GHz.

The travelling standard is supplied by SPARK. IMBIH and TÜBİTAK was responsible for analysing the data and reporting the results respectively.

IMBIH performed measurements at 50 MHz, 500 MHz, 1 GHz, 2 GHz and 3 GHz.

The reference values for the comparison were calculated using a weighted average of all participants' results. Most of the measurements matched well with these reference values.

The degrees of equivalence and E_n values are presented in the tables and graphs in the appendices. Results were considered satisfactory if $|E_n| \leq 1$.

References

- [1] JCGM 100, "Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM)", 2008.

Appendix I: Degrees of Equivalence and Normalised Errors

Table 11. The degree of equivalences (D_i), its expanded uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and the normalised errors (E_n) of the reflection coefficient S11, Real Component

0.05 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.2780713	0.0000037	0.0000005
SIQ	-0.345664873	0.000000037	-0.00000001
IMBIH	0.1978	0.000014	0.000001
0.5 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.1338797	0.0000036	0.0000002
SIQ	-0.181351682	0.000000067	-0.00000001
IMBIH	0.1227	0.000014	0.000001
1 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.0532909	0.0000034	-0.0000001
SIQ	0.00576423	0.00000017	0.00000000
IMBIH	0.0825	0.000013	0.000001
2 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.3665216	0.0000032	-0.0000006
SIQ	0.68953523	0.00000024	0.00000008
IMBIH	-0.6744	0.000013	-0.000004
3 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.3272914	0.0000032	-0.0000005
SIQ	0.42716383	0.00000024	0.00000005
IMBIH	-0.2438	0.000013	-0.000002
10 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-1.1200000	0.0000026	-0.0000014
SIQ	1.1200000	0.0000008	0.00000045
15 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.080000	0.000010	0.0000004
SIQ	-0.0800000	0.0000032	-0.00000013
18 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.5791358	0.0000094	0.0000027
SIQ	-0.5791358	0.0000052	-0.00000152

Table 12. The degree of equivalences (D_i), its expanded uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and the normalised errors (E_n) of the reflection coefficient S11, Imaginary Component

0.05 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.0994714	0.0000037	-0.0000002
SIQ	0.047895562	0.000000037	0.000000
IMBIH	0.0834	0.000014	0.000001
0.5 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.0818240	0.0000036	-0.0000001
SIQ	0.175337004	0.000000067	0.000000
IMBIH	-0.2044	0.000014	-0.000001
1 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.0303895	0.0000034	0.0000001
SIQ	-0.11888828	0.00000014	0.000000
IMBIH	0.1787	0.000013	0.000001
2 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.0000000	0.0000032	0.0000000
SIQ	0.00000000	0.00000024	0.000000
IMBIH	0.0000	0.000013	0.000000
3 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.2999558	0.0000027	-0.0000004
SIQ	0.31672772	0.00000094	0.000000
IMBIH	-0.0538	0.000013	0.000000
10 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.5303301	0.0000020	0.0000005
SIQ	-0.5303301	0.0000020	-0.000001
15 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.715542	0.000013	0.0000046
SIQ	-0.71554175	0.00000080	0.000000
18 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	1.130932	0.000011	0.0000060
SIQ	-1.1309323	0.0000032	-0.000002

Table 13. The degree of equivalences (D_i), its expanded uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and the normalised errors (E_n) of the transmission coefficient S21, logarithmic value

0.05 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.1422	0.0002	0.0000
SIQ	-0.09705	0.00010	0.00000
IMBIH	-0.0776	0.0015	0.000
0.5 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.1146	0.0002	0.0000
SIQ	-0.03693	0.00010	0.00000
IMBIH	-0.1398	0.0015	0.000
1 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.0060	0.0002	0.0000
SIQ	0.09041	0.00010	0.00000
IMBIH	-0.1583	0.0015	0.000
2 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.1650	0.0002	0.0000
SIQ	0.26273	0.00010	0.00001
IMBIH	-0.1910	0.0015	0.000
3 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.0774	0.0002	0.0000
SIQ	0.18793	0.00010	0.00001
IMBIH	-0.2107	0.0015	0.000
10 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	-0.1298	0.0001	0.0000
SIQ	0.12985	0.00041	0.00003
15 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.1623	0.0001	0.0000
SIQ	-0.16231	0.00041	-0.00003
18 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBİTAK	0.6574	0.0011	0.0000
SIQ	-0.65741	0.00066	-0.00022

Table 14. The degree of equivalences (D_i), its expanded uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and the normalised errors (E_n) of the transmission coefficient S21, phase

0.05 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	-0.0556	0.0064	-0.0002
SIQ	0.129	0.015	0.001
IMBIH	-0.120	0.082	-0.0049
0.5 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.3354	0.0079	0.0013
SIQ	-0.4438	0.0046	-0.001
IMBIH	0.240	0.085	0.101
1 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.1924	0.0056	0.0005
SIQ	-0.292	0.015	-0.002
IMBIH	0.155	0.082	-0.0064
2 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.4867	0.0056	0.0014
SIQ	-0.439	0.015	-0.003
IMBIH	-0.117	0.082	-0.0048
3 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.6579	0.0043	0.0014
SIQ	-0.494	0.031	-0.008
IMBIH	-0.341	0.081	-0.0138
10 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.24553	0.00047	0.0001
SIQ	-0.24	0.35	-0.043
15 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.40814	0.00036	0.0001
SIQ	-0.41	0.55	-0.112
18 GHz			
Labs	D_i	$U(D_i)$	E_n
TUBÍ TAK	0.53586	0.00028	0.0001
SIQ	-0.54	0.71	-0.190

Appendix II: Graphs of Degrees of Equivalence (DoE) according to the GUM

Appendix III: Comparison Reports of Participants

TÜBİTAK UME REPORT

PARTICIPANT REPORT (UME)

1. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name	TÜBİTAK UME RF & Microwave Laboratory
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E-mail	handan.sakarya@tubitak.gov.tr
Adress	TÜBİTAK UME Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah.Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No: 1 Gebze TR-41470 Kocaeli TURKEY

2. MEASUREMENT DATE

21.04.2025

3. ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION

Temperature : (23±1) °C**Relative Humidity** : (45±15) rh%

4. REFERENCES USED IN MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No	Traceability
PNA Network Analyzer	Keysight	N5225A	MY56051838	TÜBİTAK UME
Calibration Kit	Agilent	85054B	MY39200345	TÜBİTAK UME
VNA Cable	Keysight	85134-60003	50816	TÜBİTAK UME
VNA Cable	Keysight	85134-60003	50820	TÜBİTAK UME

5. MEASUREMENT METHOD

The SOLT (Short, Open, Load, Through) calibration method was used for the measurements of the standards used for determining the error terms of the VNA. The male connector of the travelling standard was measured as S11. Measurements were taken using VNA Tools II software, and uncertainty calculations were performed according to Ripple Method by using TÜBİTAK UME Excel macro software. The measurements and comparison report were carried out by Handan SAKARYA in accordance with the technical protocol of the comparison. The measurements given below are the results of the measurement taken in TÜBİTAK UME. Uncertainties are given for the real and

imaginary parts. The tables show the maximum uncertainty values for the real and imaginary quantities.

6. MEASUREMENT RESULT

Frequency (GHz)	Transmission Coefficient ($(S_{21} = S_{21} \angle \theta)$)			
	Magnitude ($ S_{21} $) (dB)	Magnitude Uncertainty (k=2)	Phase(θ) (°)	Phase Uncertainty (k=2) (°)
0.05	19.933	0.036	-3.82	0.24
0.5	19.952	0.036	-37.64	0.23
1	19.969	0.036	-75.15	0.23
2	19.995	0.036	-150.11	0.23
3	20.017	0.036	134.93	0.23
10	19.986	0.036	-34.55	0.23
15	19.975	0.036	-63.99	0.24
18	20.183	0.036	56.56	0.24

Frequency	Reflection Coefficient ($(S_{11} = x + jy)$)			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
0.05	-0.0012	0.0040	0.0000	0.0040
0.5	-0.0015	0.0040	0.0017	0.0040
1	-0.0010	0.0040	0.0043	0.0040
2	0.0040	0.0040	0.0100	0.0040
3	0.0172	0.0040	0.0062	0.0040
10	0.0102	0.0040	-0.0005	0.0040
15	0.0154	0.0080	0.0002	0.0080
18	-0.0399	0.0081	0.0577	0.0081

7. UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

7.1. Transmission coefficient measurements uncertainty budget

Model function : $S_{xy} = S_{xym} + \delta Rpr + \delta L + \delta I + \delta N + \delta M + \delta Cbl + \delta IAmb$

Attenuation value : 20 dB

Frequency : 50 MHz

Uncertainty Budget Table of 20 dB attenuator (S21) Real component @50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
Measured Value	0.10056	0.000021	Normal	1	0,000021
Reproducibility	0	0.000009	Normal	1	0,000009
Linearity	0	0.000197	Normal	1	0,000197
Isolation	0	0.000006	Normal	1	0,000006
Noise	0	0.000005	Normal	1	0,000005
Mismatch	0	0.00000007	Normal	1	0,00000007
Cable Effect	0	0.000058	Normal	1	0,000058
Ambient Conditions	0	0.000014	Normal	1	0,000014
Measured Value	0.10056	Combined Uncertainty			0.000207
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.00041

The distribution function was converted from rectangular, U-shaped, and rectangular to normal distribution for isolation, mismatch, and environmental conditions, respectively.

7.2. Reflection coefficient measurements uncertainty budget

Model function : $S_{xx} = S_{xxm} + \delta ED + \delta T + \delta L + \delta Cbl + \delta IAmb + \delta CRpr + \delta ELd$

Attenuation value : 20 dB

Frequency : 50 MHz

Uncertainty Budget Table of 20 dB attenuator (S11) Real component @50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
Measured Value	-0.00119	0.000023	Normal	1	0,000023
Effective Directivity	0	0.002	Normal	1	0,002
Tracking	0	0.000001	Normal	1	0,000001
Linearity	0	0.000007	Normal	1	0,000007
Cable Effect	0	0.0000005	Normal	1	0,0000005
Ambient Conditions	0	0.000001	Normal	1	0,000001
Connector Reproducibility	0	0.000023	Normal	1	0,000023
Effective Load Match	0	0.000048	Normal	1	0,000048
Measured Value	-0.0012	Combined Uncertainty			0.0020
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0040

In both budget table (Transmission and reflection), the biggest uncertainty given from the reel and imaginary calculations.

Connector Pin Depth Measurements

Connector	Pin Depth (inch)	Uncertainty (inch)
Input, N(Male)	-0.0004	0.0001
Output, N(Female)	-0.0013	0.0002

SIQ REPORT

PARTICIPANT REPORT (SIQ)

Participant information

Laboratory name:	Slovenian Institute of Quality and Metrology, SIQ
Related person name:	Marko Berginc
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Fax number:	/
e-mail:	marko.berginc@siq.si
Address:	SIQ Mašera-Spasičeva ulica 10 1000 Ljubljana Slovenia

Date of the measurements: 2nd July 2025

Environmental conditions:

- Temperature: 23 °C ± 2 C°
- Relative humidity: 50% ± 20%

Connector pin depths

Connector	Depth (mm)	UNC (mm)	Depth (inch)	UNC (inch)
Input, N(m)	-0.005	0.007	-0.0002	0.00027
Output, N(f)	-0.030	0.008	-0.0012	0.00032

References used in measurements

Instrument name	Manufacturers	Type/model	Serial number	Traceability
VNA	Agilent	E5061B	MY49304497	SIQ
VNA	Keysight	N5222B	MY57181626	SIQ
Short, male	Rosenberger	RPC-N 50ohm	20521	Metas
Open, male	Rosenberger	RPC-N 50ohm	22A88	Metas
Load, male	Rosenberger	RPC-N 50ohm	76B00	Metas
Short, female	Rosenberger	RPC-N 50ohm	57B97	Metas
Open, female	Rosenberger	RPC-N 50ohm	22A78	Metas
Load, female	Rosenberger	RPC-N 50ohm	76B08	Metas
Cable	Rosenberger	LU7-138-600	/	SIQ
Cable	Rosenberger	LU7-042-600	/	SIQ
Cable	Keysight	85131	60039	SIQ
Cable	Keysight	85131	60040	SIQ

For the intercomparison measurements, two VNAs, N-type calibration set, and four cables were used. The N-type calibration set is calibrated at Metas every three years to provide the traceability. The VNAs were calibrated at SIQ. The frequency of the VNA was calibrated by the counter. The counter was connected to reference time-base which is traceable to SI by ongoing intercomparison with the BIPM. The power of the VNA was calibrated by the reference power sensors which is calibrated at Metas every three years. The linearity of VNA is calibrated by reference step attenuators which are calibrated at Metas every three years. The cables are calibrated at SIQ using N-type calibration set and VNAs defined above.

The measurement of attenuation and reflection coefficient of the 20 dB attenuator was performed with custom VBA software in Excel which was used for controlling of the VNAs and for data reading. To calculate the uncertainty of the results we used software based on Monte-Carlo technique which was also written in VBA for Excel. Both programmes were written by colleagues of SIQ and were verified by comparing it to the Metas VNA Tools software.

Measurement method

The measuring method is based on S-parameter measurements using the VNA. The cables were connected to both ports of the VNA first. Afterwards, the open, short and load measurements of the setup was performed at the end of both cables with N-type reference terminations. Then a thru measurement was made by connecting both cable ends together. After obtaining all raw measurement data, a Monte-Carlo simulation based on *12-term-model* was performed to obtain calibration coefficients with corresponding uncertainties (*i.e.*, directivity, source match, reflection tracking, load match, transmission tracking and crosstalk; all for forward and reverse direction).

After completing the VNA calibration measurements, the 20 dB attenuator was attached to the measuring cables (N(m) input of the attenuator was connected to port 1 and N(f) output of attenuator to port 2 of the VNA) and four measurements were performed, between measurements the attenuator was rotated 90 degrees in the measurement setup. After obtaining the raw measurements, a Monte-Carlo simulation based on *12-term-model* was performed again to obtain the final error corrected S-parameters from which attenuation and reflection coefficients were expressed. More details about the uncertainties are given below.

The same procedure has been used twice; Agilent E5061B was used for 50 MHz measurement while the Keysight N5222B was used for the other frequencies.

Measurement results

Transmission coefficient $S_{21} = S_{21} \angle \varphi$				
Frequency (GHz)	Mag. $ S_{21} $ (dB)	Mag. unc., $k=2$ (dB)	Phase, φ (deg.)	Phase unc., $k=2$ (deg.)
0.05	19.93	0.03	-3.8	0.3
0.5	19.95	0.03	-37.7	0.2
1	19.97	0.03	-75.2	0.3
2	20.00	0.03	-150.2	0.3
3	20.02	0.03	134.8	0.4
10	19.99	0.05	-34.7	1.2
15	19.97	0.05	-64.3	1.5
18	20.16	0.06	56.1	1.7

Reflection coefficient $S_{11} = x + j \cdot y$				
Frequency (GHz)	Real comp. x	Real comp. x unc. $k=2$	Imag. comp. y	Imag. comp. y unc. ($k=2$)
0.05	-0.0018	0.0012	0.0002	0.0012
0.5	-0.0018	0.0014	0.0019	0.0014
1	-0.0009	0.0018	0.0042	0.0017
2	0.005	0.002	0.010	0.002
3	0.018	0.002	0.007	0.003
10	0.013	0.003	-0.002	0.004
15	0.015	0.006	-0.003	0.004
18	-0.043	0.007	0.052	0.006

Uncertainty Budget

The calculation of uncertainty was performed by Monte-Carlo analysis therefore uncertainty calculation with uncertainty contributions could not be given in a Table. The uncertainty contributions which are considered in the Monte-Carlo simulations for the calibration step and for the measurement step are listed below.

For the calibration step we consider the uncertainties of the open, short and load (both male and female) reference terminations which were taken from the calibration certificate (Metas). We also consider the effects of the VNAs which were taken from the calibration certificate, the effects of the cables which were taken from the calibration certificate and the effects of connectors which were taken from the literature and long-term experiences. For each of them the following contributions were considered:

VNA:

- Noise (noise floor, trace noise in magnitude and phase)

Comparison on Reflection/Transmission Coefficient

- Linearity (magnitude, phase)
- Drift since the VNA calibration

Cables:

- Reflection and transmission stability

Connector:

- Reflection and transmission stability

After Monte-Carlo analysis the calibration coefficients with corresponding uncertainties were obtained (*i.e.*, directivity, source match, reflection tracking, load match, transmission tracking and crosstalk all for forward and reverse direction).

In the measurement step we performed four measurements. For each measurement we run Monte-Carlo analysis where we considered the uncertainties related to VNA, cables and connectors as described above for the calibration phase (as in measuring phase the same uncertainty contributions are also assigned to the DUT device) and the uncertainties of calibration coefficients. After obtaining four measurement/uncertainty pairs we calculated the overall uncertainty while also considering Type A uncertainty (repeatability of the measurements).

IMBIH REPORT

PARTICIPANT REPORT (IMBIH)

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name:	Institute of Metrology of Bosnia and Herzegovina (IMBIH)
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OTHER DATA

- Location: Slovenian Institute of Quality and Metrology (SIQ)
- Temperature: $(23 \pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$
- Relative Humidity: $(50 \pm 20) \%$.
- Measurement date: 02.07.2025.

STANDARDS USED FOR MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial Number	Traceability
Vector Network Analyser 1032x	Siglent	SVA 1032x	SSA3PCCD4R0751	-
Calibration kit	Siglent	F503ME	-	-
VNA Cable	Siglent	RG58 low loss	-	-
VNA Cable	Siglent	RG58 low loss	-	-

DESCRIPTION OF MEASUREMENT METHOD

The SOLT (Short, Open, Load, Through) calibration method was used for the measurements of the standards used for determining the error terms of the VNA. The cables were connected to the ports of the VNA. After that, the open, short and load measurements of the setup was performed at the end of both cables with N-type reference terminations. Through measurement was realized by simply connecting both ends of the cables together. The male connector of the travelling standard was measured as S11. The measurements and comparison report were realized in accordance with the technical protocol of the comparison. Uncertainties are given for the real and imaginary parts. The tables show the maximum uncertainty values for the real and imaginary quantities.

Frequency (GHz)	Transmission Coefficient ($S_{21} = S_{21} \angle \theta$)			
	Magnitude ($ S_{21} $) (dB)	Magnitude Uncertainty (k=2)	Phase(θ) (°)	Phase Uncertainty (k=2) (°)
0.05	19.928	0.08	-3.85	0.6
0.5	19.945	0.08	-37.6	0.6
1	19.963	0.08	-75.12	0.6
2	19.990	0.08	-150.18	0.6
3	20.010	0.08	134.79	0.6

Frequency (GHz)	Reflection Coefficient ($S_{11} = x + jy$)			
	Real Component x	Real Component Uncertainty (k=2)	Imaginary Component y	Imaginary Component Uncertainty (k=2)
0.05	-0.0010	0.0075	0.0005	0.0075
0.5	-0.0013	0.0075	0.0011	0.0075
1	-0.0006	0.0075	0.0049	0.0075
2	0.0022	0.0075	0.0100	0.0075
3	0.0120	0.0075	0.0065	0.0075

UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

Transmission coefficient measurement uncertainty budget

Model function: $S_{21} = S_{21m} + \delta Rep + \delta Lin + \delta Isol + \delta noise + \delta M + \delta cables + \delta amb$

Attenuation value: 20 dB

Frequency: 50 MHz

Uncertainty budget 20 dB attenuator (S21) real component @50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
Measured Value	0.10067	0.0001	Normal	1	0.00010
Reproducibility	0	0.000012	Normal	1	0.00001
Linearity	0	0.0002	Normal	1	0.00020
Isolation	0	0.00001	Normal	1	0.00001
Noise	0	0.00001	Normal	1	0.00001
Mismatch	0	0.00016	Normal	1	0.00016
Cable Effect	0	0.00025	Normal	1	0.00025
Ambient Conditions	0	0.00003	Normal	1	0.00003
Measured Value	0.10067	Combined Uncertainty			0.00037
		(k=2)	Expanded Uncertainty		0.00075

Reflection coefficient measurement uncertainty budget

Model function: $S_{11} = S_{11m} + \delta_{effdir} + \delta_{tracking} + \delta_{lin} + \delta_{cables} + \delta_{ambient} + \delta_{rpc} + \delta_{ELM}$

Attenuation value: 20 dB

Frequency: 50 MHz

Uncertainty Budget 20 dB attenuator (S11) Real component @50 MHz

Definition	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
Measured Value	-0.0010	0.0001	Normal	1	0.0001
Effective Directivity	0	0.003	Normal	1	0.003
Tracking	0	0.000003	Normal	1	0.000003
Linearity	0	0.0002	Normal	1	0.0002
Cable Effect	0	0.00025	Normal	1	0.0003
Ambient conditions	0	0.00003	Normal	1	0.00003
Connector Reproducibility	0	0.0001	Normal	1	0.0001
Effective Load Match	0	0.0022	Normal	1	0.0022
Measured Value	-0.0010	Combined Uncertainty			0.0037
		Expanded Uncertainty (k=2)			0.0075

Connector Pin Depth Measurements

Connector	Pin Depth (inch)	Uncertainty (inch)
Input, N(Male)	-0.0006	0.0005
Output, N(Female)	-0.0016	0.0006